

A CONTINUUM DAMAGE MODEL TO PREDICT ULTIMATE FAILURE OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY: This paper presents a novel continuum damage model to predict the onset and propagation of intralaminar damage mechanisms in laminated composites, as well as final structural collapse. The physically-based model is formulated in the context of the thermodynamics of irreversible processes and uses damage activation functions that can accurately predict the onset of the several damage mechanisms. The model proposed is parameterized to avoid mesh dependency effects, and it is implemented in a non-linear finite element code.

KEYWORDS: Continuum damage models, Failure criteria, Fracture.

INTRODUCTION

The development of accurate models to predict the onset and propagation of damage and the structural collapse of advanced composite materials is an essential task for the reduction of the costs associated with the design and certification of composite structures. These costs are currently too high because it is necessary to perform mechanical tests at all stages of product development (building block approach). The recurring and non-recurring costs associated with composite structures can be reduced by using numerical models that are able to represent the mechanical behaviour of composites (virtual testing).

The design of composite structures for stiffness or buckling criteria is straightforward. However, this is not the case when trying to predict fracture of a composite structure. This fact is particularly important because many composite structures are strength critical. The prediction of strength in advanced composites is difficult because there are several damage mechanisms (fibre fracture, matrix transverse cracking, delamination), and structural collapse is normally the result of a process of damage accumulation and load redistribution. Therefore, continuum damage models (CDM) are being developed to address these modelling difficulties.

A CDM should provide an accurate prediction of damage onset. Some applications of composite materials, e.g. pressure vessels, do not tolerate any form of damage (for those applications, a CDM is not required, just reliable failure criteria). Failure criteria, or damage activation functions, are a fundamental part of a CDM. Accurate failure criteria should be able to represent the following characteristics of the mechanical behaviour of laminated composite materials: i) in-situ effects, i.e. the increase of transverse tensile and in-plane shear strengths

of a ply when it is embedded in a multidirectional laminate; ii) the beneficial effect of transverse compression on the apparent shear strength of a ply; and iii) the effect of shear stresses on fibre kinking. To the authors' knowledge, the only criteria that deal with all these characteristics are the LaRC03/04 failure criteria previously proposed by the authors [1]-[2].

This paper presents a novel CDM developed to predict the onset and propagation of damage in laminated composites. The model uses material properties that can be obtained from standard test methods. For example, all the ply strengths and components of the fracture toughness can be measured using ASTM standards. The use of ply properties, rather than laminate properties, is an advantage because it avoids testing laminates every time the lay-up or stacking sequence is modified.

The model accounts for crack closure effects, an important phenomenon in cases where a composite structure is subjected to multiaxial loading, and regularizes the energy dissipated to avoid mesh dependency problems and assuring the objectivity of the numerical solution. The model is formulated using an explicit integration of the constitutive model. Explicit integration is necessary to achieve the computational efficiency required for the analysis of large scale structural components.

The CDM is implemented in a non-linear finite element code, and it is able to predict the onset and type of damage, damage propagation, and structural collapse without requiring any intervention by the user during the analysis.

CONTINUUM DAMAGE MODEL

Free energy and secant tensor

To establish a thermodynamically consistent constitutive law, it is necessary to define the Gibbs free energy density in the material as a positive scalar function that is zero at the origin with respect to the free variables (the stresses). The proposed definition for the Gibbs free energy is:

$$G = \frac{\sigma_{11}^2}{2(1-d_1)E_1} + \frac{\sigma_{22}^2}{2(1-d_2)E_2} + \frac{\sigma_{12}^2}{2(1-d_6)G_{12}} - \frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} \sigma_{11} \sigma_{22} + (\alpha_{11} \sigma_{11} + \alpha_{22} \sigma_{22}) \Delta T$$

The activation of the damage variables d_i is defined by the sign of the normal stresses in the material directions:

$$d_1 = d_{1+} \frac{\langle \sigma_{11} \rangle}{|\sigma_{11}|} + d_{1-} \frac{\langle -\sigma_{11} \rangle}{|\sigma_{11}|}, \quad d_2 = d_{2+} \frac{\langle \sigma_{22} \rangle}{|\sigma_{22}|} + d_{2-} \frac{\langle -\sigma_{22} \rangle}{|\sigma_{22}|}$$

where $\langle x \rangle$ is the McCauley operator defined as: $\langle x \rangle := 1/2(x + |x|)$.

To fulfill the second principle of thermodynamics, it is necessary to guarantee a positive mechanical dissipation. Following the classical argument known as Coleman's method results in the Clausius-Duheim inequality. Applying the Legendre-Fenchel transformation, the mechanical dissipation is:

$$\Xi = \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial \sigma} - \varepsilon \right) : \dot{\sigma} + \frac{\partial G}{\partial d} \cdot \dot{d} \geq 0$$

The condition of positive dissipation is given by:

$$\Xi = \frac{\partial G}{\partial d} \cdot \dot{d} \geq 0$$

The strain tensor is obtained from the derivative of the Gibbs free energy with respect to the stress tensor:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\partial G}{\partial \sigma} = H : \sigma + \alpha \Delta T$$

The resulting compliance tensor is obtained as:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial \sigma^2} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{(1-d_1)E_1} & -\frac{\nu_{21}}{E_2} & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{21}}{E_2} & \frac{1}{(1-d_2)E_2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{(1-d_6)G_{12}} \end{bmatrix}$$

The proposed continuum damage model represents cracks in two planes for any loading history. The material orthotropy changes throughout the loading history but always keeps the same directions.

Damage activation functions

The determination of the elastic domain under complex stress states is an essential component of an accurate damage model. The stress space where material is assumed to be linear elastic is bound by four surfaces, each one accounting for one damage mechanism, as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Damage activation functions

The size of this elastic region increases with increasing damage. The damage activation functions, F_i , are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} F_{1+} &= \phi_{1+} - r_{1+} \leq 0 & F_{1-} &= \phi_{1-} - r_{1-} \leq 0 \\ F_{2+} &= \phi_{2+} - r_{2+} \leq 0 & F_{2-} &= \phi_{2-} - r_{2-} \leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

where the damage thresholds $r_{i\pm}$ take the initial value of unity when material is undamaged, and they can grow as damage progresses. These threshold values are related to the damage variables by the damage evolution laws, and they define the elastic deformations required for damage evolution.

The functions $\phi_{i\pm}$ are established in terms of the strain tensor, or in terms of the effective stress tensor, $\tilde{\sigma}$, and are defined as: $\tilde{\sigma} = C^0 : \varepsilon$, where C^0 is the undamaged plane stress stiffness tensor. The functions $\phi_{i\pm}$ are based on the LaRC04 failure criteria [1]-[2].

Longitudinal tensile fracture

The criterion used to predict longitudinal tensile fracture is defined as:

$$\phi_{1+} = \frac{E_1}{X_T} \varepsilon_{11} = \frac{\tilde{\sigma}_{11} - \nu_{12} \tilde{\sigma}_{22}}{X_T} \quad (1)$$

where X_T is the longitudinal tensile strength of a unidirectional laminate.

Longitudinal compressive fracture

The criterion used to predict longitudinal compressive fracture by formation of a kink band is defined as:

$$\phi_{1-} = \frac{\langle |\tilde{\sigma}_{12}^m| + \eta^L \tilde{\sigma}_{22}^m \rangle}{S_L} \quad (2)$$

where S_L is the in-situ shear strength of the material, which can be obtained from the closed-form solutions proposed previously by the authors [3]. The coefficient of longitudinal influence, η^L , can be determined from shear tests with varying degrees of transverse compression. In the absence of biaxial test data, η^L can be estimated from the longitudinal and transverse shear strengths, as proposed by Puck [4]:

$$\eta^L \approx -\frac{S_L \cos 2\alpha_0}{Y_C \cos^2 \alpha_0} \quad (3)$$

where Y_C is the ply compressive strength, and α_0 is the fracture angle. Typically, $\alpha_0 = 53^\circ \pm 3^\circ$. The components of the effective stress tensor are expressed in a rotated frame that is aligned with the rotation of the fibres. The components are calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\sigma}_{11}^m &= \cos^2 \varphi^c \tilde{\sigma}_{11} + \sin^2 \varphi^c \tilde{\sigma}_{22} + 2 \sin \varphi^c \cos \varphi^c |\tilde{\sigma}_{12}| \\ \tilde{\sigma}_{22}^m &= \sin^2 \varphi^c \tilde{\sigma}_{11} + \cos^2 \varphi^c \tilde{\sigma}_{22} - 2 \sin \varphi^c \cos \varphi^c |\tilde{\sigma}_{12}| \\ \tilde{\sigma}_{12}^m &= -\sin \varphi^c \cos \varphi^c \tilde{\sigma}_{11} + \sin \varphi^c \cos \varphi^c \tilde{\sigma}_{22} + (\cos^2 \varphi^c - \sin^2 \varphi^c) |\tilde{\sigma}_{12}| \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The misalignment angle φ^c is obtained as given in [1]-[2]:

$$\varphi^C = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{1 - \sqrt{1 - 4 \left(\frac{S_L}{X_C} + \eta^L \right) \left(\frac{S_L}{X_C} \right)}}{2 \left(\frac{S_L}{X_C} + \eta^L \right)} \right) \quad (5)$$

Transverse failure, $\alpha = 0^\circ$

The functions ϕ_{2+} predict the onset and evolution of matrix cracks aligned along the thickness direction of the laminate, i.e., $\alpha = 0^\circ$. This damage mechanism can be created by a combination of transverse tensile stresses and in-plane shear stresses, or by moderate values of transverse compressive stresses combined with in-plane shear stresses. Therefore, the function ϕ_{2+} is defined as:

$$\phi_{2+} = \begin{cases} \sqrt{(1-g) \frac{\tilde{\sigma}_{22}}{Y_T} + g \left(\frac{\tilde{\sigma}_{22}}{Y_T} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tilde{\sigma}_{12}}{S_L} \right)^2}, & \tilde{\sigma}_{22} \geq 0 \\ \frac{1}{S_L} \langle |\tilde{\sigma}_{12}| + \eta^L \tilde{\sigma}_{22} \rangle, & \tilde{\sigma}_{22} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where Y_T is the in-situ transverse tensile strength [3], and g is the fracture toughness ratio defined as: $g = G_{IC} / G_{IIC}$.

Transverse failure, $\alpha \neq 0^\circ$

The functions ϕ_{2-} predict the onset and evolution of matrix cracks oriented at an angle of $\alpha = 53^\circ$ with respect to the thickness direction of the ply:

$$\phi_{2-} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\tilde{\tau}_{eff}^T}{S_T} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tilde{\tau}_{eff}^L}{S_L} \right)^2}, \quad \tilde{\sigma}_{22} < 0 \quad (7)$$

where S_T is the transverse shear strength of the material, calculated as:

$$S_T = Y_C \cos \alpha_0 \left(\sin \alpha_0 + \frac{\cos \alpha_0}{\tan 2\alpha_0} \right) \quad (8)$$

The effective shear stresses on the fracture plane are defined as given in [1]-[2]:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\tau}_{eff}^T &= \left\langle -\tilde{\sigma}_{22} \cos \alpha_0 \left(\sin \alpha_0 - \eta^T \cos \alpha_0 \cos \theta \right) \right\rangle \\ \tilde{\tau}_{eff}^L &= \left\langle \cos \alpha_0 \left(|\tilde{\sigma}_{12}| + \eta^L \tilde{\sigma}_{22} \cos \alpha_0 \sin \theta \right) \right\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

with:

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{-|\tilde{\sigma}_{12}|}{\tilde{\sigma}_{22} \sin \alpha_0} \right), \quad \eta^T = -\frac{1}{\tan(2\alpha_0)} \quad (10)$$

Energy Dissipation

The dissipation is calculated as:

$$\Xi = \frac{\partial G}{\partial d} \cdot \dot{d} = Y \cdot \dot{d} \geq 0 \quad (11)$$

Where Y represents the thermodynamic forces associated with the damage variables. The model proposed here assures that the thermodynamic forces are always non-negative, i.e.:

$$\begin{aligned} Y_1 &= \frac{\partial G}{\partial d_1} = \frac{\sigma_{11}^2}{2E_1(1-d_1)^2} \geq 0 \\ Y_2 &= \frac{\partial G}{\partial d_2} = \frac{\sigma_{22}^2}{2E_2(1-d_2)^2} \geq 0 \\ Y_6 &= \frac{\partial G}{\partial d_6} = \frac{\sigma_{12}^2}{2G_{12}(1-d_6)^2} \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Therefore, the condition of positive dissipation, Eq. (11), is trivially satisfied by assuring that the damage rate is always non-negative, i.e., $\dot{d} \geq 0$.

Damage evolution

Neglecting viscous effects, the damage criteria need to be always non-positive. If $F_i < 0$, the material is in the elastic regime. When one criteria is activated ($F_i = 0$), it is necessary to evaluate the gradient $\dot{\phi}_i$. If the gradient $\dot{\phi}_i$ is non-positive, there is unloading or neutral loading. These conditions are mathematically known as Kuhn-Tucker conditions which are expressed as:

$$\dot{r}_i \geq 0 \quad F_i \leq 0 \quad \dot{r}_i F_i = 0 \quad (13)$$

When the gradient $\dot{\phi}_i$ is positive, there is damage evolution and the consistency condition, $\dot{F}_i = 0$, needs to be satisfied.

Two important characteristics of the model proposed here are that the threshold values are a function of the damage variables only, and that the loading functions depend on the strain tensor. Under these conditions, it is possible to integrate explicitly the constitutive model.

Transverse damage

The orientation of the transverse damage depends on the sign of the transverse normal stress and the relation between the compressive normal stress and the in-plane shear stress. The transverse matrix cracks aligned in the direction of the thickness of the laminate do not affect the stress transfer under compressive loads. However, matrix cracks affect the tensile response of the laminate, regardless of the orientation of the cracks. This means that the damage threshold r_{2+} is a function of the damage in the transverse direction, regardless of its orientation. Therefore, the damage thresholds for transverse damage are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Tension: } \dot{r}_{2+} &= \dot{\phi}_{2+} \text{ and } \dot{r}_{2-} = 0 \\
\text{Compression: } \dot{r}_{2+} &= \dot{\phi}_{2-} \text{ and } \dot{r}_{2+} = \begin{cases} \dot{\phi}_{2-}, & r_{2+} \leq r_{2-} \\ 0, & r_{2+} > r_{2-} \end{cases}
\end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

The integration of the previous equations results in:

$$\begin{aligned}
r_{2+} &= \max \{1, \max \{\phi_{2-}\}, \max \{\phi_{2+}\}\} \\
r_{2-} &= \max \{1, \max \{\phi_{2-}\}\}
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

Longitudinal damage

Under longitudinal tension, the damage plane is perpendicular to the loading direction. When reversing the load, the matrix cracks close and can transfer load. However, the broken fibres do not carry any additional load.

Under longitudinal compression, the damaged material, which consists of broken fibres and matrix cracks, forms a kink band, and there is not a unique orientation for the damage planes. When reversing the loads, the elastic limit increases due to the damage created under compression.

Therefore, the damage thresholds for longitudinal damage are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Tension: } \dot{r}_{1+} &= \dot{\phi}_{1+} \text{ and } \dot{r}_{1-} = 0 \\
\text{Compression: } \dot{r}_{1+} &= \dot{\phi}_{1-} \text{ and } \dot{r}_{1+} = \begin{cases} \dot{\phi}_{1-}, & r_{1+} \leq r_{1-} \\ 0, & r_{1+} > r_{1-} \end{cases}
\end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

The integration of the previous equations results in:

$$\begin{aligned}
r_{1+} &= \max \{1, \max \{\phi_{1-}\}, \max \{\phi_{1+}\}\} \\
r_{1-} &= \max \{1, \max \{\phi_{1-}\}\}
\end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

Damage laws

The damage laws result in a strain-softening constitutive model. The strain-softening characteristic of the constitutive model triggers the localization of the model and represents the cracks occurring along the thickness direction of the ply when any of the damage functions is activated.

Each damage law is parameterized with only one parameter, A_i , which must be positive. The general form of the damage laws is:

$$d_i = 1 - \frac{1}{f_i(r_i)} \exp \left[A_i (1 - f_i(r_i)) \right] f_j(r_j) \tag{18}$$

where $f_i(r_i)$ forces the softening behaviour and $f_j(r_j)$ represents the coupling between damage threshold values and damage variables occurring in the longitudinal direction.

Under transverse loading, the damage laws are defined as:

$$d_{2-} = 1 - \frac{1}{r_{2-}} \exp[A_{2-}(1-r_{2-})]$$

$$d_{2+} = 1 - \frac{1}{f(r_{2+})} \exp[A_{2+}(1-f(r_{2+}))]$$
(19)

with:

$$f(r_{2+}) = \frac{1}{2g} \left(g - 1 + \sqrt{(1-g)^2 + 4gr_{2+}^2} \right)$$
(20)

It is assumed that the damage variable d_6 depends on the density of transverse cracks. Therefore, the damage evolution law is:

$$d_6 = 1 - \frac{1}{r_{2+}} \exp[A_6(1-r_{2+})]$$
(21)

Under longitudinal loading, the damage laws are defined as:

$$d_{1+} = 1 - \frac{1}{r_{1+}} \exp[A_{1+}(1-r_{1+})]$$

$$d_{1-} = 1 - \frac{1}{r_{1-}} \exp[A_{1-}(1-r_{1-})] f(A_1^{+/-}, r_{1+})$$
(22)

with:

$$A_1^{+/-} \approx \frac{E_1 - E_2}{E_1} \text{ and}$$

$$f(A_1^{+/-}, r_{1+}) = 1 - A_1^{+/-} \frac{1}{r_{1+}} \exp[A_{1+}(1-r_{1+})]$$
(23)

Figs. 2 and 3 show the constitutive response for a loading cycle defined as O-A-B-O-C-D-O-E, for the transverse and longitudinal directions, respectively.

Fig. 2: Material response under transverse cyclic loading

Fig. 3: Material response under longitudinal cyclic loading

COMPUTATIONAL MODEL

Crack band model

It is well known that softening constitutive models create a localization of deformations in a narrow band. When implementing a softening constitutive equation in a Finite Element Model, the energy dissipated is reduced with mesh refinement. In order to overcome this problem and the corresponding lack of objectivity of the numerical model, the ‘crack band model’ proposed by Bažant [5] is used here. The constitutive model is parameterized using a characteristic dimension of the finite element, which assures that the dissipation is independent of the size of the element.

Numerical algorithm

The constitutive model developed was implemented in the ABAQUS non-linear finite element code, using a user-written subroutine (UMAT). The algorithm implemented in ABAQUS is shown in Fig. 4.

CONCLUSIONS

A constitutive model for the simulation of the degradation process of advanced composite materials was presented. This model is applicable to structures where damage localization and progressive degradation of the material result in structural collapse. Damage is represented by a fixed damage tensor where the two damage planes are defined by the material directions, longitudinal, transverse and perpendicular to the laminate mid-plane. The computation of the energy dissipated is independent of the mesh refinement, and the resulting explicit constitutive model is suitable for large scale computations.

1. Read current displacements, u_i
2. Read current strains, $\varepsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(u_{i,j} + u_{j,i})$
3. Calculate effective stresses, $\tilde{\sigma}_{ij} = C_{ijkl}^0 \varepsilon_{kl}$
4. Evaluate failure criteria, F_i
5. Calculate elastic domain thresholds, r_i
6. Calculate damage values, d_i
7. Calculate real stresses, $\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl}(d_i)\varepsilon_{kl}$
8. Calculate tangent constitutive tensor, C_{ijkl}^T

Fig. 4: Numerical algorithm

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The financial support of the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) under the project PDCTE/CTA/50354/2003 is acknowledged by the first author.

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